

Introducing Ontology-based Security Policy Management in the Grid

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Abstract: The Grid is a promising new kind of computer interconnection that aims at coordinated resource sharing and problem solving. An entity that enters the Grid remains bound to its native network and continues to abide by the corresponding security policy, while at the same time it is free to pursue its own security objectives since the Grid does not have any kind of centralized control mechanisms. As a result security management in the Grid faces three challenging new requirements: first, local security policies have to be matched to integrated Grid security policies; second, security policies are not imposed as in a top down approach, but are more of an arrangement between entities; finally, security policies are more dynamic than ever, since new entities join and leave the Grid in real time.

We believe that all three abovementioned requirements can be addressed if Grid entities are provided with appropriate models, mechanisms and tools for acquiring, processing and sharing security policy related knowledge. In this perspective, in this paper we present an ontology-based framework for enhancing security management in the Grid through security policy conceptual representation. We introduce the notion of Security Policy Ontology (SPO) and use it to demonstrate the potential and capabilities of the proposed framework: two elementary security policies are used as input; their semantically incompatible representations are then “translated” to compatible OWL descriptions that can be used for further manipulation (e.g. security policy negotiation) in a real time perspective.

Keywords: The Grid, Security Policy, Ontology, Security Management, Framework.

1. Introduction

Information systems are evolving from static, geographically confined and isolated “information islands” to dynamically formed, geographically dispersed “information spaces” that are fully interconnected; such “information spaces” are usually referred to as *virtual organizations (VOs)*. The Grid infrastructure (Global Grid Forum, 2004) is a major step towards achieving coordinated resource sharing and problem solving within, and among VOs. To achieve these goals, Grid manages intrinsic complexity by defining various abstraction layers (Foster *et al*, 2001).

Security management and configuration take place throughout those layers, and thus complicates the job of security administrators. In the lower Grid layers security interfaces exist between local systems (local security policies) and the Grid (global security policies). Matching local security policies to Grid security policies poses another important security challenge. While existing security policy conflict resolution or reconciliation frameworks have been applied within specific Grid architecture layers (Wang *et al*, 2004), - with emphasis being given in the lower, more concrete ones - little attention has been given to generic security policy management frameworks. Such a framework could address the security policy management problem throughout Grid abstraction layers, from the more concrete to the more abstract ones.

Before introducing our proposed security management enhancement framework, we elaborate the Grid security management problem in the following section, accentuating its generic perspective. In section 3, while presenting related work we make clear that security policy is a multi-interpreted notion and that various ways exist for representing security policies. We also introduce the SPO notion. We base upon this diversity to define the fundamental attributes for our framework: manipulation of security policy semantics through SPO and

uniform representation of security policies. In section 4, we present a high level, generic framework for the enhancement of security policy management in the Grid. Finally, in section 5 we conclude and present future work along with open research issues.

2. The Grid security management problem

As a revolutionary technology, the Grid poses new security concerns, not so much in terms of the appearance of novice threats but in terms of the need for increased intensity and flexibility of security mechanisms (Jackson *et al*, 2001). In this perspective one can argue that although Grid incorporates known security challenges and requirements still it introduces some new ones. Gymnopoulos *et al* present an overview of those challenges and requirements in (Gymnopoulos *et al*, 2003).

In general, security challenges in the Grid can be classified in three categories: *integration* with existing security architectures and models implemented across platforms and hosting environments, *interoperability* of multiple domains and hosting environments at protocol, policy and identity level, and *establishment of trust relationships* among the participants in a Grid system. Meeting the abovementioned security challenges, and thus effectively managing and configuring security, is a much tougher problem in the Grid than it is in classic distributed computing. This is due mainly to three characteristics of Grid computing: *dynamicity*, *autonomy* and *common goal*.

First, the formation of a VO is an entirely dynamic procedure. New resources may become available for sharing at any given time (e.g. if redeemed from another computation) just as new computational needs may occur (e.g. intense need for CPU cycles during a large-scale simulation). Second, the lack of central control allows each entity to pursue its own security objectives. Thus, the security problem is upgraded from protecting “the good from the bad” to “reconciling different security perspectives”. Finally, despite central control is absent, coordinated sharing and problem solving is still a Grid objective. Thus, above-described advanced security manipulation must be, in the general case, consistent with the need for specific qualities of service (QoS).

The above analysis indicates that generic security policy negotiation mechanisms are vital for managing security in the Grid. Especially the analysis of the last characteristic indicates that those mechanisms should, in the general case, impose the slightest possible load on Grid transactions.

3. Semantics handling in security policy representation methods – related work

As Wang *et al* note “the term ‘security policy’ has come to mean different things to different communities” (Wang *et al*, 2004). Indeed, the term “security policy” is interpreted in entirely different ways that vary from Höne’s and Eloff’s practical view of security policy as a “vital, direction giving document” (Höne and Eloff, 2002) to Bishop’s formalistic definition: “a security policy is a statement of what is, and what is not, allowed” (Bishop, 2002) and from the systemic approach presented by Kokolakis and Kiountouzis in (Kokolakis and Kiountouzis, 2000) to the specialized definition given by McDaniel and Prakash in (McDaniel and Prakash, 2002).

The existence of various interpretations is rooted in two facts. First, security policy is a context dependent notion (e.g. computer security policy, information security policy etc.) but,

also, even in the same context specific kinds of security policies have been developed to meet specific needs (e.g. confidentiality security policies in military environments etc.). Both characteristics are evidence for the abounding, in terms of *semantics*, environment that security policies exist in. Therefore, in order to manage multiple interacting security policies - and that is the case of the Grid - one has to manage first their semantics.

3.1 Related work

Along with various interpretations of the security policy notion, several methods of security policy representation exist. Suggestively we mention two polar views that adopt different scientific paradigms. Kokolakis and Kiountouzis adopt the systemic paradigm to develop a “Metapolicy Development System” (Kokolakis and Kiountouzis, 2000), while, on the other side, Gong and Qian, according to Bishop, adopt the systematic paradigm and propose axiomatic rules for the synthesis of security policies such as the “autonomy rule” and the “security rule” (Bishop, 2002). Beyond the abovementioned approaches several more exist and can be roughly divided in the following categories: Verbal Descriptions (Höne and Eloff, 2002), Modelling (Bishop, 2002), Specification (e.g. in (Damianou *et al*, 2001)), and Formalization (Bishop, 2002) (e.g. in (Treck, 2000)).

Some of the above views on security policy representation take under account the increasing use of security policies for semi or fully automated security management and thus recognize the importance of security policy semantics manipulation especially in complex environments. For example, in a very interesting paper three such views are analyzed and compared (Tonti *et al*, 2003). One of the three approaches has recently been integrated with Grid computing services on the most common Grid platform, Globus (Uszok *et al*, 2004).

One of the most interesting approaches to Grid security management using ontologies is that of the KAoS policy and domain services framework (Uszok *et al*, 2003). KAoS is a collection of componentized services. KAoS was originally developed for use with the dynamic and complex requirements of software agent applications but recently the services were adapted to general-purpose grid computing and web services environments (Uszok *et al*, 2004). The KAoS services rely on an ontology of the computational environment, application context, and the policies themselves. In KAoS, a policy is represented as an ontology instance of one of the four types of policy classes: positive or negative authorization, and positive or negative obligation.

3.2 Security Policy Ontology

The three security management challenges stated in the abstract of this paper: matching of local security policies to Grid (global) security policies, security policy negotiation, and dynamicity of the environment, can be added to the challenges posed by the nature of security policies as it was analysed in the previous subsection: multi-interpreted notion, variety of semantics and representation methods. Altogether, the challenges demonstrate the importance of security policy semantics manipulation in effectively managing security.

An efficient means for achieving semantics manipulation is ontology. Ontology is “*an explicit specification of a conceptualization*” (Gruber, 1993). *Domain-specific ontologies* are used to define the terminology for a group of people that share a common view on a specific domain (Decker *et al*, 1999), effectively supporting knowledge sharing and reuse.

Thus, security policies can be represented by the means of a Security Policy Ontology (SPO), which elaborates on the domain of security knowledge. SPOs can be used to describe

structurally heterogeneous security policies of different levels of abstraction. Thus, by defining shared and common domain theories and vocabularies, SPOs help both people and machines to communicate in a concise manner, a manner which is based not only on the syntax of security policy statements, but on their semantics, as well.

4. A framework for enhancing security management in the Grid

In the first part of this paper, we delimited its research scope within security in the Grid, we introduced the Grid security management problem, and we elaborated on the nature of security policy along with the ways in which it has been used to address the problem. We believe the analysis clearly indicates that one must deal with *security policy semantics* first in order to achieve *uniform or at least compatible representations of security policies* and through them effective management of security in the Grid.

4.1 Architecture

To address both issues mentioned above we adopt a dual architectural blueprint for the proposed framework. As shown in Figure 1 the framework blueprint consists of two layered architectural designs: the *conceptualization layer* and the *representation layer*. The former – indicated by the black colour and set in the foreground – depicts components that concern security policy semantics manipulation, while the later – indicated by the blue colour and set in the background – depicts components related to actual security policy representations.

Figure 1: The framework architecture.

Both layers consist of discrete states and transitions that lead from one state to the other. The conceptualization layer consists of four states and three transitions while the representation layer consists of three states and two transitions. From an architectural point of view there is

a correlation between states of the two layers: states 1 and 4 of the conceptualization layer correspond to states 1 and 3 of the representation layer respectively, while states 2 and 3 of the conceptualization layer correspond to state 2 of the representation layer. From a functional point of view though, the transition from one state of the representation layer to another may require the use of a state from the conceptualization layer. Finally, it should be noted that the conceptualization layer may be implemented once while the representation layer can be implemented repetitively and in an additive manner when it is required. More details about the way the two layers function are given next.

4.1.1 Conceptualization layer

The conceptualization layer of the proposed framework is depicted in Figure 2. It consists of four distinct conceptualization states and three transitions that lead from each state to the next one.

Figure 2: The conceptualization layer.

The first conceptualization state refers to nothing more than a Grid entity's security policy in its original form. As stated earlier, a security policy is a multi-interpreted notion and thus a plethora of semantics exists within various security policies. Promoting a Grid security policy to the next state requires the use of knowledge extraction techniques that will provide the necessary conceptual bedrock for the construction of a Security Policy Ontology. The specific techniques that must be used vary with the kind, scope, and morph of the original policy. In the second state, the Grid Security Policy Ontology provides a specified conceptualization that responds to the original policy but is still incompatible with the conceptualizations of other security policies at the same level. Hence, a new transition to a coordinated conceptualization is needed. This can be achieved by using several ontology merging or coordination techniques (see Appendix A). In the third state the original policy takes the form of a specific and coordinated representation of security knowledge. But since the abovementioned knowledge is structured in the form of an ontology a final transition is

required to make this conceptualization operational. This can be achieved by the transcription of the ontology to a well-structured descriptive language (e.g. to an XML based language like OWL with the Protégé tool) and thus the completion of the Grid security policy transformation from state one to state four.

While promoting a security policy through the various states of the conceptualization layer, a parallel transformation occurs in two directions: first, a set of security concepts is specified explicitly along with their relations, and second, this set is coordinated with an external set of the same kind. Regarding the transitions between states it should be noted that the first two transitions are considered as semi-automatic procedures while the last one could be fully automated.

4.1.2 Representation layer

The representation layer of the proposed framework is depicted in Figure 3. It consists of three distinct representation states (levels) and two respective transitions.

Figure 3: The representation layer.

We assume that originally a Grid entity’s security policy is represented in a specific format. As analysed in section 3.1 a plethora of different forms exist for representing security policies ranging from natural language to formal specification. In analogy with the first transition of the conceptualization layer, extraction techniques are used to promote the original representation form to state two only that here the knowledge that is sought is specific (e.g. “X.509” rather than “certificate”). The techniques are used in conjunction with the Security Policy Ontology of the second and/or third state of the conceptualization layer. The first transition results in the instantiation of the Security Policy Ontology of the second and/or third conceptualization state. The abovementioned instantiation is meant to be an additive procedure. In other words, instances that already exist in the ontology are maintained. The instantiated Security Policy Ontology (conceptualization state two) and/or the instantiated-coordinated Security Policy Ontology (conceptualization state three) can be then easily transcribed to a well-structured descriptive language (e.g. to an XML based language like OWL with the Protégé tool) and thus mark the completion of the Grid security policy representation transformation from state one to state three.

In the third state of the representation layer one can find either a uniform and structured or a uniform, structured and semantically consistent security policy representation depending on the input used, state two or three ontologies. That is if the framework is used on more than one security policies and given that uniformity and consistency are examined in terms of the relation between the two policies.

A notable difference between the two layers of the framework lies in the first transition. In the representation layer knowledge extraction involves specific security policy information in contrast with generic security notions manipulated in the respective transition of the conceptualization layer. For example, here we would talk about specific authentication methods as *passwords* or *smart cards* in contrast to the *authentication method* concept in the conceptualization layer. Finally, as regards transitions, the first transition of the representation layer can either be a highly automated procedure or even a fully automated one while the second transition could be fully automated.

4.2 Application of the proposed framework

To clarify the previously presented framework we provide an example concerning two simple Grid security policies. We assume a simple Virtual Organization, namely VO A, and a user that wishes to become a member of A and consequently access its resources. VO A and the user have distinct security policies (*conceptualization layer: first state*) that are in the general case represented in arbitrary formats (*representation layer: first state*). Here we present both policies in natural language due to simplicity reasons without harming generality as natural language is so unstructured in terms of semantics and their relationships that every security policy description can be considered as a different way of representation:

<u>User security policy</u>
<p>Authentication</p> <p>User <u>owns</u> a valid pair of identification token and password</p> <p>User <u>is provided</u> with a <i>Kerberos</i> ticket</p> <p>Authorization</p> <p>User <u>is member of</u> either group: “<i>Administrator</i>” or “<i>Restricted</i>”</p>

<u>Virtual organization A security policy</u>
<p>Authentication</p> <p>Each user that wishes to use a resource must <u>have</u>:</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">A valid pair of ID and password</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">A valid X.509 certificate</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">The X.509 certificate must be of a limited <i>duration</i></p> <p>Each resource must <u>have</u>:</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">A valid X.509 certificate</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">The X.509 certificate must be of an extended <i>duration</i></p> <p>Authorization</p> <p>Each user that <u>uses</u> resources must <u>have</u>:</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">A valid pair of ID and password</p> <p>Each user that <u>uses</u> resources that <u>belong to</u> group “<i>privilege</i>” must <u>have</u>:</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">A valid pair of ID and password</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><u>Belong to the</u> group “<i>privileged</i>”</p>

Each policy, regardless the representation method incorporates some basic security notions along with their attributes.

4.2.1 Using Security Policy Ontology

Security notions that exist in both policies along with their attributes can be extracted and used for the creation of two respective ontologies (*conceptualization layer: first transition*). The two ontologies are depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: User (top left & right) and VO (bottom left & right) Security Policy Ontology.

Although the above ontologies are specific there are notable differences in terms of semantics between them that render the conceptualizations incompatible (*conceptualization layer: second state*). For example, in the user policy ontology we see the term “ticket” while in the VO policy ontology we see the term “certificate”, in the user policy ontology the notion of a “Resource” is absent etc. To advance to the next state the use of some of the ontology coordination or merging techniques that were mentioned above is necessary (*conceptualization layer: second transition*). For the purposes of this example, we make an analogy with the example presented in (Kotis and Vouros, 2004)¹. The articulated binary relations between the ontological signatures here are $ID \equiv Token$ and $Ticket \equiv Certificate$. Given the above relations – they could be manually designated by an administrator – the coordinated ontology would be the one presented in Figure 5 (*conceptualization layer: third state*).

Figure 5: The coordinated Security Policy Ontology.

Optionally, the ontologies presented in Figure 4 could also be instantiated (*representation layer: first transition*). The ontology instances produced would then be semantically structured uniform representations of the original security policies (*representation layer: second state*). Due to limited space, we omit the presentation of this optional step.

¹ Details about this analogy are presented in Appendix A.

4.2.2 Producing compatible security policy representations

Having the merged ontology in hand we can now instantiate it by extracting specific security policy information from both security policies (*representation layer: first transition*). Since the instantiation procedure is an additive one the result should be a merged knowledge base that contains all the security notion instances that are present in both policies (*representation layer: second state*). For example, all four types of the Group notion that are present in the original policies (Administrator, Privileged, Privilege, and No Privilege) constitute separate instances of the “Group” class of the coordinated ontology. The instantiation of the coordinated Security Policy Ontology was achieved with the help of the *Protégé* tool (Gennari *et al*, 2002).

At this final stage, simple ontology transcription methods to XML based languages like OWL can be used (*conceptualization layer: third transition* and *representation layer: second transition*). The simplest way to do that is use the automated “Convert Project to Format” feature of the *Protégé* tool and select “OWL Files (.owl or .rdf)” as the intended format. Another useful way to represent the coordinated policies is through the “Create HTML” feature of the *Protégé* tool. In this way the merged ontology can be used to produce uniform security policy conceptualizations while its instantiated form can be used to produce uniform security policy representations. Below is a part of the final output of the proposed framework.

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<rdf:RDF
  xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"
  xmlns:rdfs="http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#"
  xmlns:owl="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#"
  xmlns="http://www.owl-ontologies.com/unnamed.owl#"
  xml:base="http://www.owl-ontologies.com/unnamed.owl">
  <owl:Ontology rdf:about=""/>
  <owl:Class rdf:ID="Group">
    <rdfs:subClassOf>
      <owl:Class rdf:ID="Authorization_Mechanism"/>
    </rdfs:subClassOf>
  </owl:Class>
  <owl:Class rdf:ID="Security_Mechanism"/>
  <owl:Class rdf:ID="Identification_Mechanism">
    <rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="#Security_Mechanism"/>
  </owl:Class>
  ...
```

We believe that by achieving the transformation of arbitrarily represented Grid security policies in semantically and structurally uniform representations of the above form we make a step towards the facilitation of security policy management in the Grid (e.g. semi-automated security policy negotiation).

5. Conclusions and further research

In this paper we introduced the Grid security management problem and proposed a framework for enhancing security management in the Grid using security policies. The proposed framework is based on the Security Policy Ontology notion and uses a conceptualization layer to manipulate security policy semantics and a representation layer to apply the benefits from semantics’ manipulation to the representation of security policies. In this way incompatible security policy representations can be transformed – through a series of intermediate states – to uniform representations and thus enhance our ability to manage security in the Grid. Finally, we applied the proposed framework on two simple Grid security policies, a user and a resource security policy, and highlighted its functionality.

We believe that our framework can contribute to the reduction of ambiguity concerning the interpretation of security policies that are expressed in different ways between negotiating Grid entities. The establishment of a common framework for security information exchange between Grid parties will also provide the foundations for enforcing, evaluating and auditing the security level of Grid security function in a uniform way. Moreover, such a framework will support comparable and reusable axioms between security policies, thus providing a means for semantic queries realization against a Grid policy base.

In this perspective and besides implementing in a larger scale and further testing our framework other open issues exist. For example, the way existing security policy reconciliation models can be incorporated in a generic framework, both in the general case and with specific examples, could be examined. Furthermore, an analytical mapping of the proposed framework with Grid architecture layers could be provided. Finally, we plan to investigate how such a framework can be used to produce a security policy knowledge management tool for administrators in the Grid.

Appendix A – Ontology coordination approaches

Several approaches on coordinating ontologies exist. Noy and Musen developed PROMPT, an algorithm that provides a semi-automatic approach on ontology merging and alignment by performing some tasks automatically and guiding the user to do the rest (Noy and Musen, 2000). Stumme and Maedche presented the FCA-MERGE method for merging ontologies following a bottom-up approach which offers a structural description of the merging process. What is interesting is that the FCA-MERGE method is guided by application specific instances of the given source ontologies that are to be merged (Stumme and Maedche, 2001).

In this paper we use the HCONE approach on ontology merging. The HCONE approach is based on capturing the intended informal interpretations of concepts and then exploiting the formal semantics of concepts' definitions by means of description logics' reasoning services. In general, an ontology can be considered as a pair $O=(S, A)$, where S is the ontological signature describing the vocabulary (i.e. the terms that lexicalize concepts and relations between concepts) and A is a set of ontological axioms, restricting the intended interpretations of the terms included in the signature. Ontology mapping from ontology $O_1 = (S_1, A_1)$ to $O_2 = (S_2, A_2)$ is a morphism $f:S_1 \rightarrow S_2$ of ontological signatures such that $A_2 \models f(A_1)$, i.e. all interpretations that satisfy O_2 's axioms also satisfy O_1 's translated axioms. Given two ontologies O_1 and O_2 , the HCONE approach finds an alignment between them and gets the minimal union of their (translated) vocabularies and axioms with respect to their alignment (Kotis and Vouros, 2004).

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